

CREATIVITY IN LIFE AND IN ART

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This article examines the importance of childhood in shaping a person's personality and developing their talents and abilities. It also discusses the role of theater, a distinct art form, in addressing the challenges of individuals and society.

Keywords: talent, childhood, theater, art, performance.

"Every beauty, even the slightest, even the most aimless, as well as every joyful moment of life, has great enduring value... Not a single easy, happy moment has been wasted in human life, and, consequently, in world history." I.A. Ilyin.[1]

Human beings are essentially multidimensional and complex. They comprise several layers of life: physical, mental, intellectual, and spiritual. And they are always compelled to gather themselves together, to coordinate the expressions of all their "components"—will, reason, and feelings. As in a symphony orchestra, each instrument has its own part, but they all listen to each other and yield to one another, and harmony is born. Isn't this the main goal of human creativity—to find harmony in life? As soon as human activity is deprived of ethical conditioning, it becomes meaningless. A. Schweitzer, author of works on "ethical culture," writes: "We have found ourselves captive to a disoriented thirst for activity. The spirit of our time throws us into a whirlpool of activity. It continually compels us to serve first this and then that goal, now this and then that achievement." "He deliberately inflames in us an uncontrollable thirst for activity, so that we do not come to our senses and ask what, in fact, this selfless devotion to this or that goal and achievement has in common with the meaning of the world and the meaning of our lives. Thus, like rootless and never sobering mercenaries, we wander without a worldview in the ever-thickening darkness of life, ready to serve with equal devotion both the sublime and the base." [2]

True creativity is always spiritual. It develops sensitivity of the soul, awakens conscience, and supports spirituality. In pedagogy, there is a term "education through beauty," because from a very early age, a child is most receptive to beauty, and children's creativity is absolutely perfect. An early embrace of beauty ennobles the soul, refines feelings, and makes the desire to create a pressing need. What does it mean to create? To create something new, but one's own, born of one's own creation, to become, in part, a true creator, to become like God's image. First, a child feels, then understands, appreciates, and most importantly, begins to create. Cultivating feelings is the most difficult part of a teacher's work. Creativity is not always the creation of a work of art or science; a person first feels and understands the beauty of nature, then the beauty of art, and finally comes to an understanding of the highest beauty: the beauty of man, his labor, his actions. Communion with art is one of life's greatest joys. Admiration and enjoyment of beauty naturally develop into a desire to live by the laws of beauty—to create beauty, to enjoy the beauty created with one's own hands. True labor is always creative, and beauty is an absolutely essential aspect of labor. Aesthetic perception develops into aesthetic activity. The highest degree of creativity is realized in active love. The harmony of human relationships is an act of the highest creativity. Theater is a unique art form that speaks to the beauty of human relationships. It can exist only in a specific time and space. Theater must always surprise the audience with the unexpectedness of its artistic solution, its ever-new sincerity, its unique "conventional" language. Theater is an art that makes the invisible "spiritual" manifest. An actor is a person who sees life in a unique way, possessing unique emotions, a heightened sensory world, and a unique creativity. The expression

"Theater is a school of feelings" is not an abstraction, but a real phenomenon. Truly profound theater compels both the creative team and the audience to peer into life. As an example, I would like to cite the statement about puppet theater by Hussein Vaiz-Koshifi (1440-1505), a leading scholar and thinker of Central Asia and Khorasan in the 15th century and a contemporary of Alisher Navoi: "Merry fun with games is seriousness for souls striving to discover divine mysteries..." Koshifi wrote over 200 works on poetics, astronomy, logic, literary criticism, mathematics, arithmetic, the history of Islam, theology, history, music theory, fine arts, and medicine. In his treatises, he wrote about the creative education of children, focusing on the acquisition of high moral qualities and the avoidance of negative ones.

"Whenever possible, one should strive to raise the child well, so that he or she acquires positive qualities and avoids base actions," said Koshifi. "At an early age, children are very receptive, accepting everything: good and bad. The child's soul is like a blank slate on which it is easy to draw any image." [3] Theater, music, literature, and the visual arts awaken emotional subtlety, sensitivity, and the need for aesthetic impressions in the human soul. An ancient Ukrainian proverb says: "Holding a violin in one's hands, a person is incapable of committing evil." Evil and true creativity are incompatible.

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